

Complexation Reaction of Metal Ions with Peptide Systems. Part—XI : Potentiometric Study of Complex Formation Between Ni(II), Co(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II) and Pb(II) and N-Benzoyl-Glycyl-L-Leucine

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Potentiometric studies have been carried on complexes of N-benzoyl-glycyl-L-leucine with Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II) and Pb(II) in 50% v/v dioxane-water medium at three temperatures and ionic strength 0.1M (KNO₃). Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration technique as used by Irving and Rossotti has been applied to determine stability constants of the complexes. Free energy, enthalpy and entropy changes have also been evaluated.

THE binding of metal ions to peptides has been a subject of increasing interest over the past two decades¹⁻⁶, largely because many of these reactions provide simple models for the much more complex enzymes⁷. Recently, we⁸⁻⁹ have reported the values of stability constants and thermodynamic parameters of Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II) and Pb(II) complexes with N-benzoyl-L-leucine, N-benzoyl-L-phenylalanine, N-benzoyl-glycylglycine and N-benzoyl-glycyl-L-proline. The present paper deals with the determination of stability constants and thermodynamic parameters (ΔG , ΔH and ΔS) of complexes of Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II) and Pb(II) with N-benzoyl-glycyl-L-leucine in 50% v/v dioxane-water medium at three temperatures (25 ± 0.1 , 35 ± 0.1 and $45 \pm 0.1^\circ$) and at an ionic strength of 0.1M KNO₃. The method of Calvin-Bjerrum^{10,11} as adopted by Irving and Rossotti¹² has been employed to determine logK values.

Experimental

All chemicals used were either BDH or Aldrich AnalaR quality. N-benzoyl-glycyl-L-leucine was prepared by the method of Toru Imai¹³. Dioxane was purified by the recommended procedure¹⁴. The solution of the ligand was prepared in 50% v/v dioxane-water. Metal nitrate solutions were prepared by dissolving the corresponding metal salts in doubly distilled CO₂ free water and standardized by standard volumetric methods.

pH measurements were done on Toshniwal pH meter Cl 46 having an accuracy of ± 0.01 pH units, using a glass-calomel electrode assembly in 50% dioxane-water medium at constant temperatures (25 ± 0.1 , 35 ± 0.1 and $45 \pm 0.1^\circ$) and ionic strength 0.1M(KNO₃). The pH meter was calibrated with suitable buffers before use.

The three solutions (total volume 50 ml in each case) were prepared as follows: A. 2.5 ml of

$1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ HNO₃; B. (A)+5.0 ml of $2.5 \times 10^{-3} M$ ligand and C. (A+B)+2.5 ml of $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ metal nitrate.

An appropriate quantity of potassium nitrate solution (1.0M) was added to maintain the desired ionic strength (0.1M). The above three solutions were titrated against potassium hydroxide (0.05M) solution prepared in 50% v/v dioxane-water. The three curves were obtained from the plots of pH versus volume of alkali required and curves were referred to as (i) acid, (ii) ligand, (iii) complex titration curves. The shapes of curves were as usual as shown in Fig. 1. In calculation, the concentrations were corrected for the change in volume produced by the addition of alkali during titration.

Fig. 1. Titration curves of N-benzoyl-glycyl-L-leucine at 85° and 0.1 M ionic strength.

- Scale.
X-axis: 1 cm = 0.40 ml.
Y-axis: 1 cm = 1.0 pH
- 1. Acid ○—○
 - 2. Acid + Ligand ○—○
 - 3. Acid + Ligand + Ni²⁺ □—□
 - 4. Acid + Ligand + Co²⁺ △—△
 - 5. Acid + Ligand + Zn²⁺ ●—●
 - 6. Acid + Ligand + Cd²⁺ ×—×
 - 7. Acid + Ligand + Pb²⁺ ■—■
 - 8. Acid + Ligand + Cu²⁺ ▲—▲

TABLE 1—VALUES OF PROTONATION CONSTANTS OF N-BENZOYL-GLYCYL-L-LEUCINE AND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF ITS COMPLEXES AT THREE TEMPERATURES

Metal ion	Constant	Temperature			- ΔG (K cal/mole)			- ΔH (K cal/mole)	ΔS (cal/mole/degree)
		25°	35°	45°	25°	35°	45°	at 35°	at 35°
H ⁺	Log $pK_1^{H^+}$	5.80	5.10	4.95					
Co(II)	Log K_1	2.86	2.91	2.95	3.90	4.10	4.29	1.95	19.64
Ni(II)	Log K_1	2.82	2.84	2.90	3.84	4.00	4.22	1.76	18.70
Cu(II)	Log K_1	3.21	3.28	3.29	4.88	4.62	4.79	1.69	20.49
Zn(II)	Log K_1	2.79	2.82	2.92	3.80	3.97	4.25	2.87	22.21
Cd(II)	Log K_1	2.77	2.80	2.88	3.78	3.95	4.19	2.42	20.68
Pb(II)	Log K_1	3.06	3.14	3.21	4.18	4.42	4.67	3.25	24.90

* Carboxylic functional group.

The calculated error in stability constants is $\pm 0.1 \log K$.

Results and Discussion

$\bar{n}_H$, $\bar{n}$, pL were calculated by employing the relationship derived by Irving and Rossotti¹². The proton ligand formation curve was obtained by plotting the degree of formation ($\bar{n}_H$) of the proton complex against the pH values. For N-benzoyl-glycyl-L-leucine, it has been observed that the ligand titration curve does not rise to the left of the acid titration curve, in contrast to that observed for the corresponding deprotected dipeptides. This indicates that the benzoyl group protecting amino group partially hinders zwitterion formation. Hence only a single protonation constant $pK_1^{H^+}$ (carboxylic group) was observed. The protonation constants at three temperatures were calculated by various computational methods^{11,15} and are given in Table 1.

The metal-ligand stability constants have been obtained by analysis of the formation curves obtained by plotting $\bar{n}$ versus pL . The value of $\bar{n}$ approaches 1 for all the metal complexes in the pH range 4.50-6.00, below the pH region of the hydrolysis of metal ions. This suggests that Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II) and Pb(II) form only 1:1 complexes with N-benzoyl-glycyl-L-leucine. The absence of 1:2 chelates may be due to steric hindrance offered to the in-coming second ligand molecule by the coordinated ligand in the 1:1 chelate. Bjerrum half integral method¹¹, intercalation at various $\bar{n}$ values, graphical method¹⁵ extended to dioxane-water mixture by Van Uitert and Haas¹⁶ were used to calculate the $\log K_1$ values. The values of $\log K_1$ have also been determined at three different concentrations of metal ion while keeping the ligand concentration constant. The $\log K_1$ values were found to be identical within the experimental error at all the concentrations of metal ion, indicating, thereby the formation of mononuclear complexes. The mean values of concentration stability constants ($\log K_1$) are summarized in Table 1. Benzoylation of the α -amino group markedly reduced the affinity of the ligand for metal ions. The observed $\log K_1$ values of metal complexes of N-benzoyl-glycyl-L-leucine under study

are comparable to those of corresponding metal complexes of acetates. This indicates that the benzoyl group derivative shows almost same affinity for metal ions as acetates and the amide groups do not appear to contribute to the stability of these complexes. The order of stability is Cu(II) > Pb(II) > Co(II) > Ni(II) > Zn(II) > Cd(II). The greater stability of Co(II) than Ni(II) may be attributed to the additional stabilization due to Jahn-Teller distortion present in case of Co(II) similar to Cu(II) and to favourable entropy effect, while partial oxidation of the Co(II) complexes is not absolutely ruled out. The values of $\log K_1$ increases with increase of temperature.

The values of overall changes in free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) accompanying complexation have been determined using temperature coefficient and Gibb's Helmholtz equation¹⁷ (Table 1). The error in ΔG and ΔH values lies in the range 0.2 to 0.5 Kcal/mole and that for ΔS is 0.5 cal/degree/mole. The free energies of formation (ΔG) of the complexes have more negative values with increase of temperature, showing that complex formation is a spontaneous process. Both enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) changes favour the formation of complexes.

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